

CELLULOSE ION-EXCHANGE RESINS FOR PURIFICATION AND FRACTIONATION OF PROTEINS. PART II. PREPARATION AND CHARACTERISATION OF CARBOXYMETHYL CELLULOSE FROM INDIGENOUS RAW MATERIALS

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Carboxymethylcellulose has been prepared from indigenous cellulosic raw materials and its efficiency has been tested qualitatively by column chromatography. Blotting paper and sulphite pulp appear to be satisfactory in this respect.

Semi-synthetic cellulose ion-exchange resins are typical examples of tailor-made resins which have been extensively used in column chromatography for the characterisation of protein hydrolysate. Cellulose has all the advantages of a highly cross-linked polymer. Due to extensive hydrogen bonding it behaves as a strongly knitted cross-linked polymer, insoluble in water. It has the additional advantage of a large exposed surface to help diffusion. Cellulose, however, can be made hydrophilic by suitably substituting the hydroxyl group in the chain and thereby preventing hydrogen bonding. But, if the process is carried too far, the resultant resin becomes highly hydrophilic and the whole mass becomes soluble. Best combination of properties are obtained, however, only when a small amount of substitution is effected, which results in limited swelling, thus facilitating chromatographic operation, without destroying the polymer structure.

Several cellulose derivatives have been used from time to time in ion-exchange column chromatography. Oxy-cellulose (Ott, "Cellulose", Part I, p. 158, Interscience, New York, 1954) has been found to have exchangeable carboxylic hydrogen atom and can exchange with suitable cations. Cellulose succinic half ester (McIntire and Scheuck, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 1193) and a variety of treated cottons are well known for their exchange capacity. Phosphorylated cellulose (Jurgens, Reid and Guthrie, *Textil. Res. J.*, 1948, 18, 42) has also been found to have exchange capacity as high as 1 m.e./g. Carboxymethylcellulose has been found to satisfy all the requirements of a good ion-exchange resin. Recently carboxymethyl-(CM)-cellulose, has been used by Peterson and Sober as an adsorbent in ion-exchange column chromatography for the fractionation of proteins (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 751).

EXPERIMENTAL

The following cellulosic materials were used for the preparation of carboxymethyl-cellulose:

- (a) Whatman genuine filter paper No. I.
- (b) Absorbent cotton: Mostly prepared from short staple Indian cotton, available in the market.

- (c) Egyptian raw cotton : Menaufi-52-53. Colour, dark ; staple-length 1.14/32" to 1-1/2".
- (d) Blotting paper : As available from market and is known to be made from bamboo pulp.
- (e) Sulphite pulp : Supplied by Indian Paper Pulp & Co. Ltd. and is known to be prepared from bamboo pulp.

Reagents used were (1) chloroacetic acid, (2) caustic soda bead, (3) glacial acetic acid, all analytically pure.

The cellulosic materials were analysed for their ether, alcohol-benzene extractable content, moisture and ash content. The total, α -, β - and γ -cellulose contents of each variety of the cellulosic materials were determined (Table I).

TABLE I
Analysis of starting materials.

Starting materials.	Moisture.	Ash.	% Extractable with		% Cellulose.		
			Ether.	Ethanol-benzene.	α .	β .	γ .
Filter paper	5.00%	0.053%	0.15	0.38	98.60	1.25	0.65
Absorbent cotton	5.50	0.510	0.52	0.83	97.40	2.08	1.46
Egyptian cotton	5.20	1.030	0.63	1.16	96.20	2.80	0.75
Blotting paper	5.59	0.550	0.25	0.43	94.49	1.59	3.56
Sulphite pulp.	6.10	1.050	0.49	0.78	73.90	14.80	11.60

Carboxymethylcellulose was prepared according to the method of Peterson and Sober (*loc. cit.*) in the form of a white granular powder.

Characterisation.—The active grouping in (CM)-cellulose for ion exchange is the carboxyl substituent in the ether methyl group. The exchange capacity is directly dependent on the total carboxyl content, expressed as m.e./g. of the substance. Theoretically all the three hydroxyl groups in each anhydroglucose unit of the cellulose chain may be substituted, but the most common degree of substitution ranges from 0.4 to 0.8 m.e./g. of the substance. The carboxyl content was determined by the direct acid wash method of Eyster *et al.* (*Anal. Chem.*, 1947, 19, 24).

The exchange capacities and other characteristics of (CM)-cellulose are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Starting materials.	A*.	**D.S.	Qualitative S.C. with respect to D.S.	Nature of flow.
Filter paper	0.64	0.107	Tolerable	Good flow with suction.
Absorbent cotton	0.21	0.035	Low	Good flow without suction.
Egyptian cotton	0.20	0.033	Low	Do
Blotting paper	0.55	0.092	Slight	Flow helped by suction
Sulphite pulp	0.45	0.074	Slight	Do

$$*A = \frac{(\text{c.c. of NaOH} \times N) - (\text{c.c. of HCl} \times N)}{\text{g. of substance}} = \text{m.e. of total carboxyl per g. of sample.}$$

$$** \text{ D.S.} = \text{degree of substitution} = 0.162 A / (1 - 0.058 A)$$

S.C. = swelling character.

The actual behaviour of the adsorbent as ion-exchange resin under column chromatographic conditions was studied by the method adopted as follows. (CM)-cellulose (5 g.) was made a slurry with 0.005M Na-phosphate buffer (100 c.c.) and was poured into the glass column (12" x 1"). The slurry was allowed to settle under gravity, but towards the end a compressed air pressure of 10 lbs./sq. in. was applied at the top to make the column more compact.

Freshly prepared egg-albumin solution (1%, 1 c.c.) with bromophenol blue was mixed with lyophilised haemoglobin (1 c.c.), followed by 0.005 M phosphate buffer (1 c.c.). This mixture was added dropwise to the column. The albumin solution was coloured blue due to bromophenol blue. After the addition was complete, a sharp band gradually formed at the top of the column, which slowly separated into a blue and a brownish red regions as the elution was continued with equilibrated buffer solution. Towards the end there was complete separation. The blue albumin solution was collected in one test tube and the brownish red haemoglobin was collected in another.

D I S C U S S I O N

From Table II it is seen that the exchange capacity varies depending on the physical nature of the starting material. The low exchange capacity of the two fibrous samples, e.g. absorbent cotton and Egyptian cotton, may be due to less available surface of reaction as these could not be well shredded to a fine powder owing to their very fibrous character. The other three samples were made from well shredded cellulose, and thus gave better results.

To avoid extensive degradation which caused too much swelling later on, the reaction conditions were suitably adjusted for the two materials, e.g. sulphite pulp and blotting paper. The reaction conditions were so adjusted as to give as high 'A' value as possible with minimum degradation. Since chloroacetic acid is a well-known intermicellar swelling agent, the reactions in these cases were carried out at a low temperature of -5° and the subsequent heating was done for only 25 minutes.

Extensive swelling observed with (CM)-cellulose, obtained by the usual treatment on sulphite pulp and blotting paper, may reasonably be attributed to the degrading effect of the etherifying agent as well as to lower D.P. of the starting material.

Under the column condition, low acid (CM)-cellulose gave a diffuse band and did not work well under elution conditions. But with (CM)-celluloses having 'A' values varying from 0.64 to 0.45, a sharp band was obtained and showed excellent elution characteristics with mild eluents like dilute phosphate buffers.

From the above results it may reasonably be concluded that there is a good possibility for the utilisation of the available raw materials, for the preparation of (CM)-cellulose as an ion-exchange resin. In this paper, only qualitative separation of proteins on (CM)-cellulose has been attempted. The quantitative separation is in progress and will be reported in due course.

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